

THE EFFECT OF GROWTH TEMPERATURE ON THE EPITAXIAL GROWTH BY CHEMICAL VAPOR DEPOSITION OF VERTICALLY ALIGNED ZnO NANOWIRES

So Young Yim¹, Do Han Lee¹, Samseok Jang¹, A-young Kim¹, Dongjin Byun^{1*}

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Korea University, Anam-dong, Seongbuk-gu, Seoul 136-713, Republic of Korea

* Corresponding author (dbyun@korea.ac.kr)

Keywords: *ZnO, nanowires, compressive stress, chemical vapor deposition*

1. Abstract

Vertically aligned single-crystal ZnO nanowires have been successfully grown on c-plane sapphire substrate using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) without catalyst. According to growth temperatures, it was changed ZnO growth characteristic. We investigated the effect of substrate temperatures on the growth ZnO films or nanowires on c-plane (0001) sapphire substrates. The ZnO films were acquired at 500°C, whereas the ZnO nanowires were obtained at 600°C, 700°C, and 800°C. The growth behavior diameter and growth rate of ZnO were changed due to different temperature. As a result of analyzing in-plane residual stress by X-ray diffraction, the optimized condition of ZnO nanowires were at 600°C.

2. Introduction

One dimensional semiconductor nanostructures Zinc oxide(ZnO) nanowires have attracted attention due to physical properties and diversity for potential electronic and photonic device applications such as nanolasers, field-effect transistors (FETs), gas sensors, and nanocantilevers [1]. ZnO is a II-VI metal oxide semiconductor with a direct band gap ($E_g = 3.37\text{eV}$, at 300K) and relatively large exciton binding energy (~60meV).

There is also a great interest on ZnO nanostructures, which is focused on the synthesis and characterization of the various types of growth morphologies obtained. This is because having a total of 13 fastest growth directions and a pair of {0001} polar-surfaces [2]. Wurtzite-structured ZnO has revealed to form diverse groups of morphologies such as nanobelts [3], nanocages [4], nanocombs [5], nanowires [6], and other types of nanostructures [7].

The fabrication of vertically aligned ZnO 1D structures is considered to be an effective approach for nanodevices and application on light emitting and field emission. Aligned growth of ZnO nanowires can be achieved by various methods, such as metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) [8], vapor-liquid-solid (VLS) process [9], sol-gel process [10], pulsed laser deposition [11], and chemical vapor transport(CVT) [12]. It also have been realized by both catalyst-driven (such as TiN [13], Au [14], Mn [15], NiO [16] and so on) and catalyst-free [17,18] approaches over a broad range of temperatures.

Many researchers has studied CVD process in order to growing aligned ZnO nanowires on various substrates, such as silicon [19], R-plane sapphire [20], C-plane sapphire [8,20], GaN [21], AlGaN/AlN [21], and fused silica [17, 20]. In order to grow high – quality vertical ZnO nanowires, either heteroepitaxy with an appropriate single crystalline substrate (Al_2O_3 or GaN) or homoepitaxy with a textured ZnO thin film that is deposited on top of a nonepitaxial substrate (silicon or glass) to act as a nanowire nucleation layer [22], so called epitaxy, could be used. The choice of substrate effects on the final state of strain. It is directly affected from the lattice mismatch and thermal expansion mismatch [20]. Therefore, we choose c-plane(0001) substrate.

This work reports the uncatalyzed growth method for the synthesis of vertically aligned ZnO nanowires on a c-plane (0001) sapphire substrate by CVD and analyze in-plane residual stress by X-ray diffraction.

3. Experiments

In these experiments, the CVD was used to grow nanowires on the c-plane(0001) sapphire substrate. The precursor was diethylzinc [DEZn, Zn(C₂H₅)₂] and oxygen gas (O₂). The argon gas (Ar) was used as a carrier gas triggering DEZn. During deposition, DEZn precursor is kept in a chiller cooled at 10°C and transported into the chamber by argon gas flowing at 15sccm. Oxygen gas was introduced separately into the reaction chamber. The flows of O₂ were 5sccm, and deposition pressure was 2Torr. ZnO deposited at 500-800°C and growth time was same as 30mins.

The field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Hitachi, S4800) was used to research on analysis of structure and size distribution. X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Rigaku D) with CuKα a radiation operating at 40kV, 200mA was utilized for analysis of crystalline structure. The structure properties of ZnO nanowires were determined by high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM, Tecnai 20, S-Twin) and investigated selected area electron diffraction (SAED) using the transmission electron microscope (TEM). Observing ZnO nanowires, we scraped out sapphire substrate grown ZnO nanowires with a sharp knife.

4. Results and Discussions

Figure 1 shows SEM images of the ZnO formed at different temperatures. It was grown as morphology of film at 500°C. Meanwhile it was grown to nanowires at 600°C, 700°C, and 800°C. The average diameters of the Fig 1. (b) 600°C, (c) 700°C, and (d) 800°C was 80nm, 73nm, and 33nm. Growth rate was increased and nanowires diameter was decreased with increasing temperature. This result is read that diameter becomes slight because of changing stresses. It would be figured out XRD data. The change of growth direction between 700°C and 800°C shows that increased temperature led to more growth in the stable direction. Therefore, the nanowires' bottom parts were bent.

Figure 2 shows XRD theta-2theta scan of the ZnO. XRD confirmed that the ZnO was a single crystalline and grew epitaxially. The XRD peaks in Fig. 2 are ZnO (0002), Al₂O₃ (0006), and ZnO (0004). The ZnO (0002) peak indicates that ZnO nanowires had grown on the c-plane sapphire with preferred c-axis orientations and good vertical alignment. This c-axis preferential growth is well

known as a general habit of ZnO crystal since a (0001) basal plane of ZnO has the lowest surface energy. The average full width half maximum (FWHM) of ZnO nanowires was 0.305°. It indicated that the ZnO nanowires were well aligned.

Fig. 2(a) shows that ZnO has identical crystalline structures. Fig. 2(b) shows magnified ZnO(0004) peak. However, the position of XRD peaks is slightly shifted. These phenomena happened due to different stress states [23]. From the XRD peak angles, c-axis lattice spacing can be obtained. Compare to the lattice parameter of ZnO, residual in-plane biaxial stress can be estimated via [24]

$$\sigma_{bi} = -453.6 \times 10^9 \left(\frac{c - c_0}{c_0} \right)$$

c₀ (= 0.51922nm from X-ray diffractometer, XRD Rigaku D, with CuKα a radiation operating at 40kV, 100mA) means the c-axis lattice constant of ZnO powder. The lattice constant c for hexagonal close packed ZnO is equal to twice the interplanar spacing, d, of the basal plane, measured from the position of the (0002) peak using the Bragg equation.

From the XRD results, the lattice constant of the c-axis of the ZnO grown under 500°C, 600°C, 700°C and 800°C are c=5.1660 Å, 5.2098 Å, 5.2068 Å, and 5.2038 Å in Fig. 3. The ZnO powder lattice constant is 5.1922 Å. It shows that the lattice constant difference between ZnO powder and grown ZnO makes stress characteristic changed. Since ZnO nanowires's lattice constant was similar to ZnO powder's lattice constant, the ZnO nanowires characterized as defect-free.

The table 1 is stress profile at different c-lattice constant. This result showed that there were thin film at 500°C in high tensile (+2285.879MPa) stresses. It also pointed that 600°C, 700°C, and 800°C nanowires were in high residual in-plane compressive (-1537.567MPa, -1275.482MPa, -1013.397MPa) stresses. Compressive stresses decreases with growing of temperature from 600°C to 800°C. It is the reason why ZnO diameter becomes thin in Fig. 1 SEM image. That is, increasing length of ZnO nanowires results in ZnO nanowires diameter decreases in same ZnO nanowires volume during the same growth time and amount of source. Therefore the optimized condition of ZnO nanowires growth was 600°C.

Figure 4 shows TEM images of ZnO nanowires at 600°C. The cross SEM image of ZnO nanowires and the lower-magnification TEM images obtained for ZnO nanowires are shown in Fig. 1(b, inset) and Fig. 3(a). The ZnO nanowires length was $650\text{nm} \pm 30\text{nm}$. This results showed that ZnO nanowires were cut off in the process of manufacture sample. The structural characterization of the ZnO nanowires was performed by high-resolution TEM in Fig. 3(b). It shows the lattice fringes and the selected-area electron diffraction pattern (SAED) of ZnO nanowires. The lattice spacing of about 0.26nm between adjacent lattice planes corresponds to the d-spacing of ZnO (0002) crystal planes [25]. It can be seen that the ZnO crystal lattices are well aligned c-axis orientation preferentially. A selected-area diffraction pattern also indicates that ZnO nanowires are single crystal with wurtzite structure and reveals the growth direction is along the [0001] direction.

5. Conclusion

The ZnO was epitaxially formed on sapphire (0001) substrates by CVD. The growth behavior of ZnO was changed because of different temperature while ZnO was growing. According to increasing the growth temperature, ZnO diameter was decreased and growth rate was increased. The ZnO nanowires showed c-plane crystal orientation which was examined by XRD measurement. The result of nanowires at 600°C tends to have high residual in-plane compressive stresses. By analyzing TEM, ZnO nanowires were well aligned c-axis orientation preferentially. It has been found that increase of crystalline can be achieved by 600°C. These nanowires were characterized by good in-plane alignment single crystalline. Due to good alignment of 600°C nanowires, the application of ZnO nanowires could be adjust to light-emitting applications such as nanolasers, field-effect transistors (FETs), gas sensors, nanocantilevers, light emitting, and field emitters.

Fig.1. Top and cross-sectional (insets) SEM images of ZnO grown at (a) 500°C, (b) 600°C, (c) 700°C, and (d) 800°C.

Fig 2. XRD θ - 2θ scans of ZnO showing (a) from the left, peaks of ZnO(0002), Al_2O_3 (0006), and ZnO(0004), and (b) the ZnO(0004) peak of samples prepared at 500°C, 600°C, 700°C and, 800°C.

Fig. 3 ZnO lattice constants at growth temperatures of (a) 500°C, (b) 600°C, (c) 700°C, and (d) 800°C vs. ZnO powder.

Table 1. Stress characterization of ZnO film and nanowires from XRD data.

Growth temperature(°C)	Morphology	c-lattice constant (Å)	Stress (MPa)
500	Thin film	5.1660	+2288.879
600	Nanowires	5.2098	-1537.567
700	Nanowires	5.2068	-1275.482
800	Nanowires	5.2038	-1013.397

Fig. 4 TEM images of ZnO: (a) low-magnification; (b) high-resolution, showing single crystalline nanowires with [0002] growth direction. Inset shows selected-area electron diffraction pattern.

References

- [1] Hadis Morkoc. And Umit Ozgur “Zinc Oxide”, WILEY-VCH, 2009.
- [2] Jijun Qiu, Xiaomin Li, Weizhen He, Se-Jeong Park, Hyung-Kook Kim, Yoon-Hwae Hwang, Jae-Ho Lee and Yang-Do Kim “The growth mechanism and optical properties of ultralong ZnO nanorod arrays with a high aspect ratio by a preheating hydrothermal method”, Nanotechnology, Vol 20, pp 155603-155611, 2009.
- [3] Xiaogang Wen, Yueping Fang, Qi Pang, Chunlei Yang, Jiannong Wang, Weikun Ge, Kam Sing Wong, and Shihe Yang “ZnO Nanobelt Arrays Grown Directly from and on Zinc Substrates: Synthesis, Characterization, and Applications”, Journal of Physical Chemistry B, Vol 109, pp 15303-15308, 2005.
- [4] Snure, Michael; Tiwari, and Ashutosh “Synthesis, Characterization, and Green Luminescence in ZnO Nanocages”, Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, Vol 7, No 2, pp 481-485, 2007.
- [5] F Liu, P J Cao, H R Zhang, J Q Li and H J Gao “Controlled self-assembled nanoaeroplanes, nanocombs, and tetrapod-like networks of zinc oxide”, Nanotechnology, Vol15, pp 949-952, 2004.
- [6] Zhong Lin Wang “ZnO nanowire and nanobelt platform for nanotechnology”, Materials Science and Engineering R, Vol 64, pp 33-71, 2009.
- [7] Z. L. Wang “Zinc Oxide Bulk, Thin films and Nanostructures”, Elsevier, oxford, 2006.
- [8] Park J Y, Yun Y S and Hong Y S “Synthesis, electrical and photoresponse properties of vertically well-aligned and epitaxial ZnO nanorods on GaN-buffered sapphire substrates”, Applied Physics Letters, Vol 87, No. 123108, 2005
- [9] Pu Xian Gao and Zhong L. Wang “Substrate Atomic-Termination-Induced Anisotropic Growth of ZnO Nanowires/Nanorods by the VLS Process”, Journal of Physical Chemistry B, Vol 10, No 23, pp 7534-7537, 2004.
- [10] G.S. Wua,b, T. Xiea, X.Y. Yuana, Y. Lia, L. Yanga, Y.H. Xiaoa and L.D. Zhanga “Controlled synthesis of ZnO nanowires or nanotubes via sol-gel template process”, Solid State Communications, Vol 134, pp 485-489, 2005.
- [11] Ye Sun and Michael N R Ashfold “Photoluminescence from diameter-selected ZnO nanorod arrays”, Nanotechnology, Vol 24, No 18, pp 245701-245705, 2007
- [12] Peidong Yang, Haoquan Yan, Samuel Mao, Richard Russo, Justin Johnson, Richard Saykally, Nathan Morris, Johnny Pham, Rongrui He, and Heon-Jin Choi “Controlled Growth of ZnO nanowires and Their Optical Properties”, Advanced functional materials, Vol 5, No. 12, pp 323-331, 2002.
- [13] P. X. Gao, Y. Ding, and Z. L. Wang “Crystallographic Orientation-Aligned ZnO Nanorods Grown by a Tin Catalyst”, Nano Letters, Vol 9, No 9, pp1315-1320, 2003.
- [14] Y. W. Wang, L. D. Zhang, G. Z. Wang, X. S. Peng, Z. Q. Chu and C. H. Liang “Catalytic growth of

- semiconducting zinc oxide nanowires and their photoluminescence properties”, *Journal of Crystal Growth*, Vol 234, Issue 1, pp171-175, 2002.
- [15] H. L. Yan, X. L. Zhong, J. B. Wang, G. J. Huang, S. L. Ding, G. C. Zhou, and Y. C. Zhou “Cathodoluminescence and room temperature ferromagnetism of Mn-doped ZnO nanorod arrays grown by chemical vapor deposition”, *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol 90, pp082503-082505, 2007.
- [16] Seung Chul Lyu, Ye Zhang, Hyun Ruh, Hwack-Joo Lee, Hyun-Wook Shim, Eun-Lyung Suh, and Cheol Jin Lee “Low temperature growth and photoluminescence of well-aligned zinc oxide nanowires”, *Chemical Physics Letters*, Vol 363, pp134-138, 2002.
- [17] Jih-Jen Wu and Sai-Chang Liu “Catalyst-Free Growth and Characterization of ZnO Nanorods”, *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, Vol 106, pp9546-9551, 2002.
- [18] F. C. Tsao, J. Y. Chen, C. H. Kuo, G. C. Chi, C. J. Pan, P. J. Huang, C. J. Tun, B. J. Pong, T. H. Hsueh, C. Y. Chang, S. J. Pearton, and F. Ren “Residual strain in ZnO nanowires grown by catalyst-free chemical vapor deposition on GaN/sapphire (0001)”, *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 92, p 203110, 2008.
- [19] Kwang-Sik Kim, and Hyoun Woo Kim “Synthesis of ZnO nanorod on bare Si substrate using metal organic chemical vapor deposition”, *Physical B*, Vol 328, pp 368-371, 2003.
- [20] V. Srikant, and D.R Clarke “Optical absorption edge of ZnO thin film : The effect of substrate”, *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol 81, No. 9, pp 6357-6364, 1997.
- [21] Xudong Wang, Jinhui Song, Peng Li, Jae Hyun Ryou, Russell D. Dupuis, Christopher J. Summers, and Zhong L. Wang “Growth of Uniformly Aligned ZnO Nanowire Heterojunction Arrays on GaN, AlN, and Al_{0.5}Ga_{0.5}N Substrates”, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, Vol 127, pp7920-7923, 2005.
- [22] Lori E. Greene, Matt Law, Dawud H. Tan, Max Montano, Josh Goldberger, Gabor Somorjai, and Peidong Yang “General route to vertical ZnO nanowire arrays using textured ZnO seeds”, *Nanoletters*, Vol 5, No 7, pp 1231-1236, 2005
- [23] Min-Chang Jeong, Byeong-Yun Oh, Woong Lee, and Jae-Min Myoung “Comparative study on the growth characteristics of ZnO nanowires and thin films by metalorganic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD)”. *Journal of Crystal growth*, Vol. 268, pp149-154, 2004.
- [24] M.K Puchert, P.Y. Timbrell, and R.N. Lamb “Postdeposition annealing of radio frequency magnetron sputtered ZnO films”. *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A*, Vol 14, No 4, 1996.
- [25] Sai-Chang Liu and Jin-Jen Wu “Low-temperature and catalyst-free synthesis of well-aligned ZnO nanorods on Si(100)”, *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, Vol. 12, pp 3125-3129, 2002.